

OVERCOMING STRESS DURING COVID-19: Maintain mental health reduce long-term effects

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7586343>

ABSTRACT

The mental health assessment of children and adolescents by the Department of Mental Health found that 28% of children and adolescents were highly stressed, 32% were at risk of depression, and 22% were at risk of suicide. In Thailand, the suicide rate increased from 2017, from 4.94 per hundred thousand people to 5.33 per hundred thousand people in 2018.

According to the Rajanagarindra Institute of Child and Adolescent Mental Health, Thailand has only about 200 child and adolescent psychiatrists serving in government agencies compared to 15 million adolescents.

Approximately 30-50% of patients who have recovered from COVID still have symptoms such as fatigue, fatigue, fever, cough, headache. This condition is called Long Covid, which many cases have psychological symptoms. and may affect life in the long run.

Keywords: Anxiety, COVID-19, mental health

Feelings of fear, anxiety, and stress are common and often occurring in situations where we are faced with uncertainty. or things that we cannot predict These feelings can happen to people who have experienced the COVID-19 pandemic. Whether it's an infected person or in the environment of an infected person.

COVID-19 situation has changed the lives of many people in this era, such as having to work from home (Work from Home) or many people having to become

Multidisciplinary Scientific Journal of Biology, Pharmacy and Health

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ISSN Number: (2965-0607)

unemployed. Children cannot go to school and have to study online. Everyone has to keep a distance in their lives. With these different situations, each person is stressed. Especially those who have already been infected with COVID-19, not only need to take good care of their physical health. Mental health also needs to be closely monitored.

Taking care of your mental health through the COVID crisis

Mental health is an important part of living a balanced and healthy life. In the era of COVID, it leads to various concerns. Although stress in crisis situations is a natural mechanism, But not to let go without a response plan. That's because it can lead to a lot of risks. both against oneself and others.

Dr. Apisamai Srirangsan , a psychiatric specialist Provides information about the high levels of stress caused by the COVID situation. The most common is When patients come to see a psychiatrist, they are afraid of infection. Feeling paranoid Whether it's people in the house, someone close to them, some people are even suspicious of themselves. Often overly anxious and not knowing when this situation will end cause most people the most stress.

For patients with pre-existing mental health problems, they are more at risk of exacerbation if stressed out. “There is information before the COVID crisis. The World Health Organization (WHO) reported at the beginning of 2020 that around the world there are approximately 264 million people suffering from depression , with Thailand experiencing an increase in suicide rates from 2017 , 4.94 per 100,000 population to 5.33 per 100,000 population. People in 2018 (1)

Multidisciplinary Scientific Journal of Biology, Pharmacy and Health

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ISSN Number: (2965-0607)

Women and children were hit hardest

The World Health Organization reports that Some people may have multiple sources of stress. Since the feeling of loneliness that must be cut off from society to be separated from loved ones Mixed with the fear of infection, fear of serious illness or death. In addition, the lack of financial liquidity is another important factor that causes stress and anxiety that affect overall mental health.

Recent research from the Global Burden of Disease reveals how COVID - 19 is affecting the mental health of young people. causing them to think of suicide Or have self-harming behavior. It was also found that it had a serious effect on physical health. and the hearts of women than men (2).

In Thailand, the results of the mental health assessment of children and adolescents by the Department of Mental Health found that 28% of children and adolescents were highly stressed, 32% were at risk of depression, and 22% were at risk of suicide. A survey by UNICEF also found that 7 out of 10 Thai children and youth have worse mental health. Which is affected by the COVID- 19 epidemic , most of them are concerned with family income, schooling, education and future employment.

“Children and adolescents in Thailand and around the world are increasingly facing mental health issues, but mental health issues are often ignored. or has been overlooked or even concealed because it is still a stigmatized or embarrassing matter despite the fact that it should be taken seriously and was brought up as a normal thing To encourage children and youth who face mental health problems to

Multidisciplinary Scientific Journal of Biology, Pharmacy and Health

www.biofarma.med.br

ISSN Number: (2965-0607)

access essential services more conveniently. and faster, ” said Kyeong-san Kim, Director of UNICEF Thailand.

UNICEF's report, The State of the World's Children 2021; On My Mind: promoting, protecting and caring for children's mental health, points out that At least 1 in 7 children worldwide has been affected by lockdown measures. while more than 1.6 billion children face learning disruptions (3).

Meet with a psychiatrist to assess stress

Lack of knowledge and awareness of mental health coupled with stigma and a lack of mental health resources. As a result, many children and young people are not encouraged to have good mental health. or get help when facing mental health problems According to the database of the Rajanagarindra Institute of Child and Adolescent Mental Health, Thailand has only about 200 child and adolescent psychiatrists serving in government agencies compared to 15 million adolescents.

WHO director of mental health and fiscal affairs, Devora Kestel, said that wherever there is an outbreak of COVID- 19 must pay attention to mental health “Each country should ensure that Mental health remedies are accessible to all populations. if they want.”

Dr. Apisamai suggested that if oneself or someone close to one of the mental health patients or suspected to be already ill During this time, you should visit a psychiatrist to assess your symptoms and treat them appropriately. If you have regular appointments, you shouldn't stop seeing your doctor. Because if left untreated, it can lead to severe and dangerous symptoms. The way to cope with stress that everyone

Multidisciplinary Scientific Journal of Biology, Pharmacy and Health

www.biofarma.med.br

ISSN Number: (2965-0607)

can do is Let's start by not making the situation worse. by making big or important decisions should take good care of yourself and be careful not to get infected with COVID.

In addition, the doctor does not recommend consuming too much news. “ Choose to receive news from reliable institutions, check Fake News , and strictly follow the recommendations of the Ministry of Public Health. Both about maintaining cleanliness, distance, and wearing a hygienic mask. avoid touch and regularly check their own mental and emotional state. Try to live a normal and valuable life. Try to do something useful, constructive, not stress yourself out.”(4)

' 4 Create 2 Use ' helps to take care of the mind during the COVID treatment.

Mental health personnel should be involved in the processes of mental care for patients and health workers in hospitals. to provide mental support and psychosocial appropriately Structuring should include activities that are consistent with the mental health and psychosocial needs framework. (Emotional state of the person expressing) to others to see from basic to specialist services. taking into account safety, human rights, human dignity equality and values of society and culture There is a consistent integrated work. Emphasis on coordinating network partners to help forward.

Mental care during COVID-19 quarantine includes physical health care. in order to recover or improve symptoms and apply the principle of “ 4 created , 2 used” as a guideline for mental care in the face of crises, consisting of build 1 build security Ensuring members to follow the rules of safety since social distance Always wash

Multidisciplinary Scientific Journal of Biology, Pharmacy and Health

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ISSN Number: (2965-0607)

your hands with soap/alcohol. wear a mask all the time and clean surfaces that your hands touch.

Create 2 Create peace by choosing reliable news and spending time with the media appropriately. Including practicing relaxation techniques suitable for yourself.

Build 3 Build Expectations by ensuring that able to prevent and resolve obstacles.

build 4 build sympathy Take care of each other regardless of race, religion or occupation. There are volunteers available to help and encourage. May switch roles as leaders in organizing activities to promote each other's encouragement.

Use 1 Use your potential to the fullest. Prepare to work/earn income after treatment.

Use 2. Use bonds to build strength. Have a communication group to exchange with each other regularly, such as writing messages to encourage each other. Encourage family contact and exchange feelings and concerns that arise (5).

The Long Covid situation takes time to recuperate

According to the information of approximately 30-50% of patients who have recovered from COVID, it is found that there will still be residual symptoms such as fatigue, fatigue, fever, cough, headache. This condition is called Long Covid (Long Covid) which can be found in patients. 4-12 weeks after infection In addition to physical symptoms Many patients also have psychological symptoms. and may affect lifestyle Especially in patients with severe COVID-19 symptoms that require hospitalization in the intensive care unit (ICU) or intubation. There may be a mental disorder. Slow recovery, inflexibility, not doing what you want to do, like having to "lock down" your own life.

Multidisciplinary Scientific Journal of Biology, Pharmacy and Health

www.biofarma.med.br

ISSN Number: (2965-0607)

Patients affected by Long COVID often need time to recuperate. Basic agility may be lost, causing loss of confidence in daily life. Many people tend to feel tired more easily. When you lose confidence in what you've done, resulting in reduced interactions with others and inevitably affecting the mind. Until the state of anxiety or depression. Some people feel guilty that they have to take sick leave for a long time, and colleagues have to take responsibility instead. This can affect mental health in the long run.

Long Covid also results in brain fatigue or Brain Fog. This condition is caused by brain symptoms. That may manifest as slow decision-making, such as feeling slow, blurry, or wandering. They often have memory problems. Indecisiveness, short attention span, wandering mind, indifference to surroundings, headache, confused thoughts.

Approximately 1 in 4 recovered from COVID-19 has a mental disorder, with 18 percent having anxiety and 13.6 percent having emotional problems, and 5.4 percent had insomnia while some people experience a combination of symptoms which these symptoms affect daily activities and lifestyle of patients directly (6).

Close people - family helps heal the mind

Because long covid affects mental health. Therefore, it is essential to receive special care. In both cases under treatment or in the recovery period after recovering from illness. It's based on the same approach as how you deal with normal stress, such as when you feel stressed, anxious, or in a mood that's unusual. Maybe find an opportunity to ask someone to go for a walk around the house, talk to family

Multidisciplinary Scientific Journal of Biology, Pharmacy and Health

www.biofarma.med.br

ISSN Number: (2965-0607)

members or distant friends over the phone or use various applications to relieve stress.

You should also refrain from watching or following stressful news. or have a negative effect on the mind finding a hobby. Do activities that help you concentrate. get enough sleep. Going to bed and waking up at an important time should refrain, reduce or avoid drinking alcohol. Try to set a goal to do each day. Maybe something that is easy to do when you can achieve your goals will make you feel more proud of yourself. Don't keep stress in your heart. It's a good idea to talk to family or friends when you feel that your mental state is not normal. It will help reduce the mood that is depressed, stressed or depressed.

If following the instructions above and still not recovering from mental collapse should not be left but consult a doctor In which the doctor will talk and ask questions for diagnosis, give advice and recommend correct actions. The doctor may also provide treatment along with medication to reduce the condition as well.

For those who have relatives or close people who have been sick with COVID or have symptoms of COVID-19 Have to observe the behavior of the patient to see if there is a mental disorder or not. In order to prevent mental health problems of patients. Some of them may be severe to the point of self-harm or suicide. When it is found that the patient has started to have symptoms, the patient should be taken to seek treatment from a doctor (7).

Being physically ill is not as difficult to heal as being mentally ill. Mental health issues are not shameful. should hurry out of stress And if you can't manage it yourself, you need to consult a doctor. before it's too late.

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DR. SUPREDA ADULYANON CHIEF EXECUTIVE OFFICER THAI HEALTH PROMOTION FOUNDATION Bangkok, Thailand Dr. Supreda Adulyanon is one of the leading experts in innovative health financing and health promotion movement in Thailand and Asia. He is well known internationally for his work on supporting countries on sustainable health financing mechanism, and on addressing major health risks control for NCDs in Thailand, such as tobacco and alcohol. Currently, he is the Chief Executive Officer of the Thai Health Promotion Foundation (ThaiHealth), the forefront national agency which catalyzes, motivates, supports, and coordinates health promotion movement in Thailand to over 20,000 multi-sectoral partner organizations in Thailand and abroad since 2001. Prior to joining ThaiHealth, he was a lecturer and senior administrator at the Faculty of Dentistry, Khon Kaen University, Khon Kaen, Thailand. He served as the Deputy Chief Executive Officer of ThaiHealth and its Director of the Major Risk Factors Control section, overseeing Tobacco Control Plan, Alcohol Control Plan and Road Traffic Accident Prevention Plan at the ThaiHealth. He was instrumental in Thailand achievements and improvement in reducing the national health burden derived from those three major risk factors. On academia front, and has written and published numerous articles about health promotion and the innovative health financing model.

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Multidisciplinary Scientific Journal of Biology, Pharmacy and Health

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ISSN Number: (2965-0607)

